

Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 9 (0000 up to 8888)

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Historic Overview

Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Inder Taneja published five papers on arXiv (for 1 up to 11111):

ARXIV Version	Evaluated Range	Allowed Operations	Missing Increasing	Missing Decreasing	Valid Representations
1 (06-02-2013) ¹	44 to 1000	+ * ^	2	10	1902 (of 1914)
2 (19-03-2013) ²	44 to 4444	+ * ^	50	53	8699 (of 8802)
3 (05-06-2013) ³	44 to 11111	+ * ^ ()	590	605	20941 (of 22136)
4 (05-08-2013) ⁴	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () -	449	315	21460 (of 22224)
5 (08-01-2014) ⁵	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () - /	9	10	22205 (of 22224)

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (for -2147483647 up to 2147483647):

Date	Title
12-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Exhaustive Search ⁶
14-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Negative Integers ⁷
18-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Without Subtraction and/or Division ⁸

Inder Taneja published three papers on RGMIA (for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
12-09-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ⁹
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20001 to 25000 ¹⁰
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 25001 to 30000 ¹¹

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (comparing results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
06-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: 11112 up to 30000 ¹²

Inder Taneja published two papers on Zenodo (combining results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
18-01-2019	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ²⁸
03-02-2019	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20000 to 30000 ²⁹

Authors published six papers on Figshare/Zenodo (improving our previous work):

Date	Title
14-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Simplifications (01) ¹³
24-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (01) ¹⁴
02-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (02) ¹⁵
28-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (03) ²⁵
06-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (04) ³⁰
07-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (05) ³¹

Historic Overview

Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Tim Wylie published one paper on arXiv (focusing on bases 3 through 10):

Date	Title
11-10-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations of Numbers for Small Bases ¹⁶

Authors published six papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 11 through 16):

Date	Title
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 (0000 up to AAAA) ¹⁷
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 12 (0000 up to BBBB) ¹⁸
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 13 (0000 up to CCCC) ¹⁹
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 14 (0000 up to DDDD) ²⁰
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 15 (0000 up to EEEE) ²¹
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (0000 up to FFFF) ²²

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (completing the base 11 up to 16 series):

Date	Title
09-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 up to 16 (0000 up to XXXX) ²³

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (extending the base 16 series):

Date	Title
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (-FFFFFF up to FFFFF) ²⁴

Authors published two papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 17 through 62):

Date	Title
23-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 36 (0000 up to #####) ²⁶
02-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 62 (0000 up to #####) ²⁷

Base 9 Crazy Sequential Representation

For example, two valid base 9 crazy sequential representations:

$$\frac{23_{10} \quad 25_9}{1_9/2_9*((-3_9+4_9)^{5_9}+67_9)-8_9} \qquad \frac{36_{10} \quad 40_9}{(8_9-7_9)^{6_9}*(-5_9+43_9)+2_9/1_9}$$

For clarity, the corresponding base 10 representations:

$$\frac{1_{10}/2_{10}*((-3_{10}+4_{10})^{5_{10}}+61_{10})-8_{10}}{(8_{10}-7_{10})^{6_{10}}*(-5_{10}+39_{10})+2_{10}/1_{10}}$$

Definition

Valid mathematical expression, thus well-formed interpretable syntactic construct.
Evaluation results is an integer value, thus a number without a fractional component.
Notation as used by most programming languages, thus restricted to following characters:

$$1 \quad 2 \quad 3 \quad 4 \quad 5 \quad 6 \quad 7 \quad 8 \quad + \quad - \quad * \quad / \quad ^ \quad (\quad)$$

Digits 1 up to 8 occur in **increasing** or **decreasing** order:

$$\frac{1/2*((-3+4)^5+67)-8}{(8-7)^6*(-5+43)+2/1}$$

Digits represent **single-digit** or **multi-digit** numbers (concatenation of digits is allowed):

$$\frac{1/2*((-3+4)^5+67)-8}{(8-7)^6*(-5+43)+2/1}$$

Numbers occur in **positive form** or **negative form** (negation of numbers by “-” is allowed).

$$\frac{1/2*((-3+4)^5+67)-8}{(8-7)^6*(-5+43)+2/1}$$

Allowed operations; **addition**, **subtraction**, **multiplication**, **division** and/or **exponentiation**.

$$\frac{1/2*((-3+4)^5+67)-8}{(8-7)^6*(-5+43)+2/1}$$

Order of evaluation may be influenced by **parentheses** (also nested parentheses).

$$\frac{1/2*((-3+4)^5+67)-8}{(8-7)^6*(-5+43)+2/1}$$

Representations with **negation** of **segments in brackets** are referred to as “pseudo”.

$$\begin{array}{l} (1+2-3)*(45*(-(6^7)+8)) \qquad (8+7*-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1) \\ (1+2-3)*(45/-(6^7)+8) \qquad (8+7/-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1) \\ (1+2-3)*(45^-(6^7)+8) \qquad (8+7^-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1) \\ (-(1+2)+3)*(45^(6^7)+8) \qquad (8+7^(6^5)+4)*(-(3-2)+1) \\ -(1-2+234*(5-6-7+8)) \qquad -((8-7-6+5)*43-2+1) \end{array}$$

Representations without negation of segments in brackets are referred to as “genuine”.

Aim

Identify genuine base 9 crazy sequential representations for 0000_9 , up to 8888_9 ,

Expected number of representations = $2_9 + 8888_9 + 8888_9 = 20000_9 = 13122_{10}$

Results

13011_{10} out of 13122_{10} were identified, see supplement.

Missing

Increasing ₉	4458, 4475, 4736, 5274, 5283, 5386, 5850, 6067, 6141, 6267, 6322, 6323, 6354, 6367, 6372, 6404, 6425, 6426, 6481, 6488, 6652, 6717, 6718, 6723, 6727, 6761, 7242, 7375, 7417, 7430, 7434, 7463, 7472, 7502, 7506, 7507, 7544, 7678, 7681, 7704, 7757, 7781, 7805, 7806, 7807, 7855, 7867, 7868, 8011, 8082, 8127, 8132, 8162, 8166, 8545, 8555, 8563, 8581, 8614, 8631, 8652, 8653, 8660, 8662, 8684, 8708, 8741, 8742, 8743, 8747
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Decreasing ₉	6237, 6553, 7137, 7211, 7307, 7344, 7354, 7375, 7378, 8055, 8073, 8105, 8136, 8145, 8155, 8182, 8235, 8247, 8248, 8275, 8433, 8543, 8544, 8545, 8554, 8563, 8566, 8567, 8575, 8608, 8645, 8703, 8713, 8805, 8806, 8823, 8828, 8830, 8831, 8837, 8838
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Discussion

The “first integers that can not be sequentially represented under the defined operations” were identified “through brute force search” by Tim Wylie¹⁶ and published on arXiv:

Base	Increasing	Decreasing	Neither
3	0	0	0
4	13	11	16
5	27	17	27
6	67	77	92
7	260	262	292
8	614	809	1192
9	3293	4570	5414
10	10958	14324	21212

Tim Wylie¹⁶ allowed “negation of an expression” during brute force search, while authors focused on “genuine crazy sequential representations”, which by definition do not allow “negation of an expression”. Nevertheless, identical “first integers” were identified:

Base	Increasing	Decreasing	Neither
9	$4458_9 = 3293_{10}$	$6237_9 = 4570_{10}$	$7375_9 = 5414_{10}$

Note

Authors consider base 9 crazy sequential representations to be proof-of-work, as identification is computationally expensive, while verification is trivial. Authors did not simplify and/or optimize the crazy sequential representations.

Authors do not guaranty:

- Published crazy sequential representations are the shortest in existence.
- Published crazy sequential representations are in their simplest form.
- Unavailable crazy sequential representations do not exists.

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